

Supporting information

Carbon Substituted Amines of the Cobalt Bis(dicarbollide) Ion; Stereochemistry and Acid-Base Properties

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Table of Contents

Experimental Instrumental Techniques	5
Single Crystal X-Ray Diffraction	5
NMR Spectroscopy	6
HR-MS.....	6
I. Single Crystal X-Ray Diffraction	10
Crystal data and structure refinement for Me ₄ N[(1,1'-N ₃ C ₂ H ₄ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N10)	10
Crystal data and structure refinement for [Me ₄ N][(1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C ₂ H ₄ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N11)	11
Crystal data and structure refinement for [Me ₄ N][(1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C ₆ H ₆ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N12).....	13
Crystal data and structure refinement for anionic Me ₄ N[(1-NH ₂ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N4) and protonated form Me ₄ N[(1-NH ₂ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)].HCl.1/2MeOH (Me ₄ N4.HCl).....	15
A. Anionic Me ₄ N[(1-NH ₂ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N4)	15

B. Protonated form [Me ₄ N][(1-NH ₂ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)].HCl (Me ₄ N4.HCl).....	17
Crystal data and structure refinement for Me ₄ N[(1,1'-H ₂ N-1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N5)...	20
Crystal data and structure refinement for [Me ₄ N][(1-H ₂ N-CH ₂ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)].2HCl (VIII).....	24
Crystal data and structure refinement for [Me ₄ N][(1-H ₂ N-C ₂ H ₄ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)].HCl (Me ₄ NIII).....	27
II. NMR Spectra	30
NMR Spectra of [Me ₄ N][(1-N ₃ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N2).....	30
NMR Spectra of [Me ₄ N][(1,1'-N ₃ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N3).....	33
NMR Spectra of [Me ₄ N][(1-H ₂ N-1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N4).....	36
NMR Spectra of [Me ₄ N][(1,1'-NH ₂ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N5).....	39
NMR Spectra of [Me ₄ N][(1-Me ₃ Si-1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N6)	42
NMR Spectra of [Me ₄ N][(1,1'-Me ₃ Si-1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N7)	45
NMR Spectra of [Me ₄ N][(1-N ₃ -C ₂ H ₄ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N8)	49
NMR Spectra of [Me ₄ N][(1-N ₃ -C ₃ H ₆ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N9).....	52
NMR Spectra of [Me ₄ N][(1,1'-N ₃ -C ₂ H ₄ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N10).....	54
NMR Spectra of [Me ₄ N][(1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C ₂ H ₄ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N11).....	57
NMR Spectra of [Me ₄ N][(1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C ₃ H ₆ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N12)	60
NMR Spectra of [Me ₄ N][(1-(CO)N ₃ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N13).....	62
III. HR-MS SPECTRA	65
HRMS Spectrum of [(1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)] ⁻ (1 ⁻)	65
HRMS Spectrum of [(1-N ₃ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] ⁻ (2 ⁻)	66
HRMS Spectrum of [(1,1'-N ₃ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)] ⁻ (3 ⁻).....	67
HRMS Spectrum of [(1-H ₂ N-1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] ⁻ (4 ⁻)	68
HRMS Spectrum of [(1,1'-NH ₂ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)] ⁻ (5 ⁻)	69
HRMS Spectrum of [(1-Me ₃ Si-1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] ⁻ (6 ⁻)	70
HRMS Spectrum of [(1,1'-Me ₃ Si-1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)] ⁻ (7 ⁻).....	71
HRMS Spectrum of [(1-N ₃ -C ₂ H ₄ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] ⁻ (8 ⁻).....	72
HRMS Spectrum of [(1-N ₃ -C ₃ H ₆ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] ⁻ (9 ⁻).....	73
HRMS Spectrum of [(1,1'-N ₃ -C ₂ H ₄ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)] ⁻ (10 ⁻).....	74
HRMS Spectrum of [(1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C ₂ H ₄ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] ⁻ (11 ⁻).75	
HRMS Spectrum of [(1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C ₃ H ₆ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] ⁻ (12 ⁻).76	
HRMS Spectrum of [(1-(CO)N ₃ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] ⁻ (13 ⁻).....	77

List of Figures

Figure S1. The crystal structure of [Me ₄ N][(1,1'-N ₃ C ₂ H ₄ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N10).	11
Figure S2. The crystal packing in the structure of Me ₄ N[(1,1'-N ₃ C ₂ H ₄ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N10)	11
Figure S3. The crystal structure of [Me ₄ N][(1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C ₃ H ₆ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)].CH ₂ Cl ₂	13
Figure S4. The crystal packing in the structure of [Me ₄ N][(1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C ₂ H ₄ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)]	13
Figure S5. The crystal structure of Me ₄ N[(1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C ₃ H ₆ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)].CH ₂ Cl ₂	14
Figure S6. The crystal packing in the structure of Me ₄ N[(1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C ₃ H ₆ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)].CH ₂ Cl ₂	15
Figure S7. The crystal structure of the anionic form of Me ₄ N[(1-NH ₂ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)](Me ₄ N4).	17
Figure S8. The crystal packing in the structure of racemic crystal of Me ₄ N[(1-NH ₂ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me ₄ N4).....	17
Figure S9. The crystal structure of [Me ₄ N][(1-NH ₂ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)].HCl (Me ₄ N4).HCl.....	19
Figure S10. The major (left) and minor (right) components in the structure of [Me ₄ N][(1-NH ₂ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)].HCl (Me ₄ N4).HCl	19
Figure S11. Crystal packing in the structure of [Me ₄ N][(1-NH ₂ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)].HCl (Me ₄ N4).HCl.....	20
Figure S12. The crystal structure of the protonated form of Me ₄ N[(1,1'-NH ₂ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)].HCl (Me ₄ N5).HCl.....	22
Figure S13. The crystal packing in the structure of Me ₄ N[(1,1'-NH ₂ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)].HCl (Me ₄ N5).HCl.....	22
Figure S14. The crystal structure of the protonated form of [Me ₄ N][(1,1'-NH ₂ -CH ₂ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)].HCl (Me ₄ N5).HCl	26
Figure S15. The formation of hydrogen bonds between the amino groups and the hydrochloride moiety in the structure of Me ₄ N[(1-H ₂ N-CH ₂ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)].2HCl.2H ₂ O.....	27
Figure S16. The crystal packing in the structure of Me ₄ N[(1-H ₂ N-CH ₂ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁) ₂ -3,3'-Co(III)].HCl	27
Figure S17. The presence of hydrogen bonds between the amino groups and the chloride anion in the structure of Me ₄ N[(1-H ₂ N-C ₂ H ₄ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₀)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)].HCl.....	29
Figure S18. The crystal packing in the structure of [Me ₄ N][(1-H ₂ N-C ₂ H ₄ -1,2-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₁)(1',2'-C ₂ B ₉ H ₁₂)-3,3'-Co].HCl	29
Figure S19. ¹¹ B{ ¹ H} NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N2 in CD ₃ OD	30
Figure S20. ¹¹ B NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N2 in CD ₃ OD	30
Figure S21. ¹ H NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N2 in CD ₃ OD	31
Figure S22. ¹ H{ ¹¹ B} NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N2 in CD ₃ OD	32
Figure S23. ¹³ C{ ¹ H} NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N2 in CD ₃ OD	32
Figure S24. ¹¹ B{ ¹ H} NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N3 in CD ₃ OD	33
Figure S25. ¹¹ B NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N3 in CD ₃ OD	33
Figure S26. ¹ H NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N3 in CD ₃ OD	34
Figure S27. ¹ H{ ¹¹ B} NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N3 in CD ₃ OD	35
Figure S28. ¹³ C{ ¹ H} NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N3 in CD ₃ OD	35
Figure S29. ¹¹ B{ ¹ H} NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N4 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	36
Figure S30. ¹¹ B NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N4 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	36
Figure S31. ¹ H NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N4 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	37
Figure S32. ¹ H{ ¹¹ B} NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N4 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	38

Figure S33. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N4 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	38
Figure S34. $^{11}\text{B}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N5 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	39
Figure S35. ^{11}B NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N5 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	39
Figure S36. ^1H NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N5 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	40
Figure S37. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N5 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	41
Figure S38. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N5 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	41
Figure S39. $^{11}\text{B}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N6 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	42
Figure S40. ^{11}B NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N6 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	42
Figure S41. ^1H NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N6 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	43
Figure S42. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N6 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	43
Figure S43. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N6 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	44
Figure S44. $^{29}\text{Si}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N6 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	44
Figure S45. $^{11}\text{B}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N7 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	45
Figure S46. ^{11}B NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N7 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	45
Figure S47. ^1H NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N7 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	46
Figure S48. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N7 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	47
Figure S49. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N7 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	48
Figure S50. $^{29}\text{Si}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N7 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	48
Figure S51. $^{11}\text{B}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N8 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	49
Figure S52. ^{11}B NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N8 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	49
Figure S53. ^1H NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N8 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	50
Figure S54. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N8 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	50
Figure S55. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N8 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	51
Figure S56. $^{11}\text{B}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N9 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	52
Figure S57. ^{11}B NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N9 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	52
Figure S58. ^1H NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N9 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	53
Figure S59. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N9 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	53
Figure S60. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N9 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	54
Figure S61. $^{11}\text{B}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N10 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	54
Figure S62. ^{11}B NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N10 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	55
Figure S63. ^1H NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N10 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	55
Figure S64. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N10 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	56
Figure S65. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N10 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	56
Figure S66. $^{11}\text{B}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N11 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	57
Figure S67. ^{11}B NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N11 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	57
Figure S68. ^1H NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N11 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	58
Figure S69. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N11 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	58
Figure S70. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N11 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	59
Figure S71. $^{11}\text{B}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N12 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	60
Figure S72. ^{11}B NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N12 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	60
Figure S73. ^1H NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N12 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	61
Figure S74. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N12 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	61
Figure S75. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N12 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	62
Figure S76. $^{11}\text{B}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N13 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	62
Figure S77. ^{11}B NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N13 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	63
Figure S78. ^1H NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N13 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	63
Figure S79. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me ₄ N13 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	64
Figure S80. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of Me ₄ N13 in (CD ₃) ₂ CO.....	64
Figure S81. HRMS spectrum of 1 ⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.....	65
Figure S82. HRMS spectrum of 2 ⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.....	66
Figure S83. HRMS spectrum of 3 ⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.....	67

Figure S84. HRMS spectrum of 4⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.....	68
Figure S85. HRMS spectrum of 5⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.....	69
Figure S86. HRMS spectrum of 6⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.....	70
Figure S87. HRMS spectrum of 7⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.....	71
Figure S88. HRMS spectrum of 8⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.....	72
Figure S89. HRMS spectrum of 9⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.....	73
Figure S90. HRMS spectrum of 10⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.....	74
Figure S91. HRMS spectrum of 11⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.....	75
Figure S92. HRMS spectrum of 12⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.....	76
Figure S93. HRMS spectrum of 13⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.....	77

Experimental

Instrumental Techniques

Single Crystal X-Ray Diffraction

Data of compounds **4⁻**, **5⁻**, and **10⁻** to **12⁻** and **III** were collected on the Rigaku XtaLAB Synergy S diffractometer equipped with micro-focus with Cu radiation (Cu/K α λ = 1.54184 Å) and a Hybrid Pixel Array Detector (HyPix-6000HE). An Oxford Cryosystems (Cryostream 800) cooling device was used for data collection and the crystals were kept at 100.00(10) K during data collection. CrysAlisPro software¹ was used for data collection, cell refinement and data reduction and absorption correction. Data were corrected for absorption effects using empirical absorption correction (spherical harmonics), implemented in SCALE3 ABSPACK scaling algorithm and numerical absorption correction based on Gaussian integration over a multifaceted crystal model.² The structures of compounds **4⁻**, **5⁻**, and **10⁻** to **12⁻** were solved with the ShelXT³ structure solution program using Intrinsic Phasing and refined with the SHELXL⁴ refinement package using Least Squares minimisation implemented in Olex2.⁵ Anisotropic displacement parameters were refined for all non-H atoms. The hydrogen atoms were calculated to idealized positions in the residual electron density map. For crystallographic data and structure refinement see ESI, Tables S1 to S6. Molecular graphics for the structures of **4⁻**, **5⁻**, and **10⁻** to **12⁻** and **III⁻** in ESI were generated using DIAMOND software (Version 4.6.8).⁶ The crystallographic data of the structural analysis have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, CCDC Nos. 2359154 to 2359160.

The full set of diffraction data for **VIII** was collected at 150(2)K with a Bruker D8-Venture diffractometer equipped with Mo (Mo/K α radiation; λ = 0.71073 Å) microfocus X-ray (I μ S) source, Photon III CMOS detector and Oxford Cryosystems cooling device was used for data collection. The frames were integrated with the Bruker SAINT software package using a narrow-frame algorithm. Data were corrected for absorption effects using the Multi-Scan method (SADABS). Obtained data were treated by XT-version 2019/1 and SHELXL-2019/3 software implemented in APEX4 v2022.2-0 (Bruker AXS) system. Hydrogen atoms were mostly localized on a difference Fourier map, however to ensure uniformity of treatment of crystal, all hydrogens were recalculated into idealized positions (riding model) and assigned temperature factors $H_{iso}(H) = 1.2 U_{eq}$ (pivot atom) or of $1.5 U_{eq}$ (methyl). H atoms in methyl, methylene moieties and hydrogen atoms in B-H or C-H moieties of clusters were placed with C-H or B-H distances of 0.96, 0.97 and 1.1 Å, and refined freely for all N-H and O-H atoms. The crystallographic data of the structural analysis have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, CCDC No. 2374900.

Selected interatomic distances and angles are given in Figs. 2 to 6 captions and the details about the particular structures are provided in Supporting Information. Crystallographic parameters for each

compound given in Tables S1 to S9 and the crystal structures and crystal packing are depicted in Figures SF1 to SF18. The deposit nos. in CCDC are given as a reference in Tables S1 to S9.

Supplementary crystallographic data can be obtained free of charge via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif, or by emailing data_request@ccdc.cam.ac.uk, or by contacting The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; fax: + 44 1223 336033.

NMR Spectroscopy

Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy measurements were done on JEOL 600 MHz spectrometer. The spectra of all compounds were measured after dissolution in deuterated-acetone unless otherwise stated. ^{11}B NMR (193 MHz) chemical shifts are given in ppm to high-frequency (low field) to $\text{F}_3\text{B}\cdot\text{OEt}_2$ as the external reference. Residual solvent ^1H resonances were used as internal secondary standards. The NMR data are presented in the text as follows: ^{11}B NMR: ^{11}B chemical shifts δ (ppm), multiplicity. ^1H NMR (600 MHz) and ^{13}C (151 MHz): chemical shifts δ are given in ppm relative to the standard Me_4Si (0 ppm), coupling constants $J(\text{H},\text{H})$ are in Hz.

HR-MS

High-Resolution Mass Spectrometry (HRMS) spectra were recorded by an Orbitrap ExplorisTM 120 spectrometer equipped with heated electrospray ionization (HESI) in negative mode using nitrogen (5.0 Messer) as a collision gas. For HESI-MS, solutions of concentration approximately $100\text{ ng}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ in acetonitrile were introduced by infusion into the ion source from a syringe. Molecular ions $[\text{M}]^-$ were detected for all univalent anions as base peaks in the spectra. By comparison, the experimental isotopic distribution in the boron plot of the peaks in the measured spectra corresponded fully to the calculated spectral pattern. The data are presented for the most abundant mass in the boron distribution plot (100%) and for the signal corresponding to the m/z value. Conditions used for the HESI interface: vaporizer temperature $50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; N_2 (isolated from air in Genius XE35, Peak Scientific) as a nebulizing sheath gas and auxiliary gas, flow $3.22\text{ L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ and $6.12\text{ L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, respectively; ion spray voltage 3500 V ; capillary temperature $280\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and mass range from 100 to 1200.

I. Experimental

Degradation of the azide ion 2^- in solution.

1. Weighed sample of the azide, Me_4N_2 (1.0 mg) was dissolved in 1.0 mL of 50% aqueous MeOH in a screw-cap vial of volume 1.6 mL and the vial was shaken for 5 days. Samples for analysis were taken every 24h and then analyzed using LC-MS system Orbitrap ExplorisTM 120. Analytical results after 2nd and 5th day are depicted in Figure S1. It can be seen, that the compound was almost completely degraded after five days (Figure S1). The main products of degradation identified by HRMS of the column effluent at maximum peak height include ions $[\text{C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{12}]^-$, $[\text{C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3]^-$ and $[(1\text{-NH}_2\text{-}1,2\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(1',2'\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-}3,3'\text{-Co(III)}]^-$ (Figure S2). The composition of some smaller peaks could not be identified using HRMS.
2. The sample of Me_4N_2 (50 mg) was dissolved in 50% aqueous MeOH (15 mL) in a screw-cap vial of volume 20 mL and the solution was stirred for 3 days at room temperature. Then the solution was concentrated on a rotary evaporator and dissolved in minimum volume of MeOH and injected onto LC column Buchi RP (80 g) for flash chromatography and eluted with 50% aqueous MeOH. The first fraction contained the main fraction of the 11-vertex *nido*-species along with some other degradation products. The composition was analyzed by HRMS and the

spectrum is shown in Figure S3. Unfortunately, further attempt to isolate pure compounds from this fractions were unsuccessful.

Figure S1. LC–MS chromatograms showing analytical separation of the degradation products in the sample of Me₄N₂ ($t_R = 13.49$ min.) of concentration 1mg/mL in MeOH/H₂O (1:1, b. v.) after 0, 2, and 5 days. Chromatographic conditions: column Kinetex C18 100 Å (2.6 μm, 150 × 2.1 mm I.D.), mobile phase: 5.0 mM propyl amine acetate (pH: 4.5) in 65% aqueous CH₃CN, flow rate, 0.15 mL/min., detection DAD at 228 nm.

Figure S2. HRMS analysis of the column effluent corresponding to the peaks of main degradation products, from top to bottom: $[C_2B_9H_{11}N_3]^-$ ($t_R = 2.05$ min.), $[C_2B_9H_{12}]^-$ ($t_R = 2.83$ min.), and $[(1-NH_2-1,2-C_2B_9H_{10})(1',2'-C_2B_9H_{11})-3,3'-Co(III)]^-$ ($t_R = 5.44$ min.). The calculated MS spectra of the individual degradation products are shown in green color below each experimentally measured spectrum (in black).

Figure S3. HRMS analysis of the first chromatographic fraction from RP-chromatography of the larger sample of Me₄N₂ (on top). The bottom part shows experimental (black) and calculated boron plot corresponding to the individual molecular peaks of the *nido*-anions [C₂B₉H₁₁N₃]⁻ and [C₂B₉H₁₂]⁻; the calculated peaks are shown in green color and given below the each experimentally determined molecular peak.

II. Single Crystal X-Ray Diffraction

Crystal data and structure refinement for Me₄N[(1,1'-N₃C₂H₄-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₁)₂-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me₄N10)

Experimental

Single crystals of C₁₂H₄₀B₁₈CoN₇ were grown from CH₂Cl₂-Hexane. A suitable crystal was selected and measured on a XtaLAB Synergy, Dualflex, HyPix diffractometer, Rigaku. The crystal was kept at 100.00(10) K during data collection. Using Olex2 [1], the structure was solved with the SHELXT [2] structure solution program using Intrinsic Phasing and refined with the SHELXL [3] refinement package using Least Squares minimisation.

Crystal Data for C₁₂H₄₀B₁₈CoN₇ (*M* = 536.02 g/mol): triclinic, space group P-1 (no. 2), *a* = 7.3363(4) Å, *b* = 12.9448(4) Å, *c* = 14.5047(5) Å, α = 93.565(3)°, β = 92.462(4)°, γ = 93.027(4)°, *V* = 1371.40(10) Å³, *Z* = 2, *T* = 100.00(10) K, μ (Cu K α) = 5.026 mm⁻¹, *D*_{calc} = 1.298 g/cm³, 16517 reflections measured (6.112° ≤ 2 θ ≤ 154.7°), 5363 unique (*R*_{int} = 0.0550, *R*_{sigma} = 0.0537) which were used in all calculations. The final *R*₁ was 0.0511 (*I* > 2 σ (*I*)) and *wR*₂ was 0.1483 (all data).

Table S1 Crystal data and structure refinement for Me₄N10.

Crystal data

Identification code	CCDC 2359156
Empirical formula	C ₁₂ H ₄₀ B ₁₈ CoN ₇
Formula weight	536.02
Temperature/K	100.00(10)
Crystal system	triclinic
Space group	P-1
<i>a</i> /Å	7.3363(4)
<i>b</i> /Å	12.9448(4)
<i>c</i> /Å	14.5047(5)
α /°	93.565(3)
β /°	92.462(4)
γ /°	93.027(4)
Volume/Å ³	1371.40(10)
<i>Z</i>	2
ρ _{calc} /cm ³	1.298
μ /mm ⁻¹	5.026
F(000)	556.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.22 × 0.15 × 0.1

Data collection and refinement

Radiation	Cu K α (λ = 1.54184)
2 θ range for data collection/°	6.112 to 154.7
Index ranges	-9 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 9, -15 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 10, -17 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 17
Reflections collected	16517
Independent reflections	5363 [<i>R</i> _{int} = 0.0550, <i>R</i> _{sigma} = 0.0537]
Data/restraints/parameters	5363/0/347
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.097
Final <i>R</i> indexes [<i>I</i> ≥ 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	<i>R</i> ₁ = 0.0511, <i>wR</i> ₂ = 0.1392
Final <i>R</i> indexes [all data]	<i>R</i> ₁ = 0.0600, <i>wR</i> ₂ = 0.1483
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	0.50/-0.76

Figure S4. The crystal structure of $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][(\text{1,1}'\text{-N}_3\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})_2\text{-3,3}'\text{-Co(III)}]$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N10}$) (ORTEP view, 30% probability level).

Figure S5. The crystal packing in the structure of $\text{Me}_4\text{N}[(\text{1,1}'\text{-N}_3\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})_2\text{-3,3}'\text{-Co(III)}]$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N10}$) containing a pair of enantiomers. (ORTEP view, 40% probability level).

Crystal data and structure refinement for $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][(\text{1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C}_2\text{H}_4\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(\text{1}',\text{2}'\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3}'\text{-Co(III)}]$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N11}$)

Experimental

Single crystals of $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{47}\text{B}_{18}\text{Cl}_2\text{CoN}_4$ were grown from CH_2Cl_2 -Hexane. A suitable crystal was selected and measured on a XtaLAB Synergy, Dualflex, HyPix diffractometer, Rigaku. The crystal was kept at 100.00(10) K during data collection. Using Olex2 [1], the structure was solved with the SHELXT [2] structure solution program using Intrinsic Phasing and refined with the SHELXL [3] refinement package using Least Squares minimisation.

Crystal Data for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{43}\text{B}_{18}\text{CoN}_4$ ($M=569.07$ g/mol): monoclinic, space group $\text{P2}_1/\text{c}$ (no. 14), $a = 13.14020(10)$ Å, $b = 18.42780(10)$ Å, $c = 12.74000(10)$ Å, $\beta = 95.6700(10)^\circ$, $V = 3069.83(4)$ Å³, $Z = 4$, $T = 100.00(10)$ K, $\mu(\text{Cu K}\alpha) = 4.493$ mm⁻¹, $D_{\text{calc}} = 1.231$ g/cm³, 121290 reflections measured ($6.76^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 161.148^\circ$), 6668 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0449$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.0142$) which were used in all calculations. The final R_1 was 0.0332 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and wR_2 was 0.0940 (all data).

Table S2 Crystal data and structure refinement for Me₄N11.

Crystal data	
Identification code	CCDC 2359158
Empirical formula	C ₁₈ H ₄₃ B ₁₈ CoN ₄
Formula weight	569.07
Temperature/K	100.00(10)
Crystal system	monoclinic
Space group	P2 ₁ /c
a/Å	13.14020(10)
b/Å	18.42780(10)
c/Å	12.74000(10)
α/°	90
β/°	95.6700(10)
γ/°	90
Volume/Å ³	3069.83(4)
Z	4
ρ _{calc} /cm ³	1.231
μ/mm ⁻¹	4.493
F(000)	1184.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.26 × 0.15 × 0.1

Data collection and refinement	
Radiation	Cu Kα (λ = 1.54184)
2θ range for data collection/°	6.76 to 161.148
Index ranges	-16 ≤ h ≤ 16, -23 ≤ k ≤ 23, -16 ≤ l ≤ 16
Reflections collected	121290
Independent reflections	6668 [R _{int} = 0.0449, R _{sigma} = 0.0142]
Data/restraints/parameters	6668/0/374
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.088
Final R indexes [I ≥ 2σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.0332, wR ₂ = 0.0931
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.0344, wR ₂ = 0.0940
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	0.33/-0.39

Figure S6. The crystal structure of $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][(\text{1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C}_3\text{H}_6\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(\text{1',2'-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3'-Co(III)}].\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ (ORTEP view, 30% probability level).

Figure S7. The crystal packing in the structure of $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][(\text{1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C}_2\text{H}_4\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(\text{1',2'-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3'-Co(III)}]$ showing the presence of two independent enantiomers (ORTEP view, 40% probability level).

Crystal data and structure refinement for $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][(\text{1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C}_6\text{H}_6\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(\text{1',2'-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3'-Co(III)}]$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N12}$)

Single crystals of $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{47}\text{B}_{18}\text{Cl}_2\text{CoN}_4$ were grown from CH_2Cl_2 -Hexane. A suitable crystal was selected and measured on a XtaLAB Synergy, Dualflex, HyPix diffractometer, Rigaku. The crystal was kept at 100.00(10) K during data collection. Using Olex2 [1], the structure was solved with the SHELXT [2] structure solution program using Intrinsic Phasing and refined with the SHELXL [3] refinement package using Least Squares minimisation.

Crystal Data for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{47}\text{B}_{18}\text{Cl}_2\text{CoN}_4$ ($M = 668.02$ g/mol): orthorhombic, space group $Pbca$ (no. 61), $a = 13.8107(2)$ Å, $b = 16.8363(2)$ Å, $c = 29.2184(5)$ Å, $V = 6793.89(17)$ Å³, $Z = 8$, $T = 99.99(10)$ K, $\mu(\text{Cu K}\alpha) = 5.552$ mm⁻¹, $D_{\text{calc}} = 1.306$ g/cm³, 55240 reflections measured ($6.05^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 160.458^\circ$), 7296 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0519$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.0294$) which were used in all calculations. The final R_1 was 0.0431 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and wR_2 was 0.1203 (all data).

Table S3. Crystal data and structure refinement for Me₄N12.

Crystal data	
Identification code	CCDC 2359157
Empirical formula	C ₂₀ H ₄₇ B ₁₈ Cl ₂ CoN ₄
Formula weight	668.02
Temperature/K	99.99(10)
Crystal system	orthorhombic
Space group	Pbca
a/Å	13.8107(2)
b/Å	16.8363(2)
c/Å	29.2184(5)
α/°	90
β/°	90
γ/°	90
Volume/Å ³	6793.89(17)
Z	8
ρ _{calc} /cm ³	1.306
μ/mm ⁻¹	5.552
F(000)	2768.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.175 × 0.155 × 0.098

Data collection and refinement

Radiation	Cu Kα (λ = 1.54184)
2θ range for data collection/°	6.05 to 160.458
Index ranges	-17 ≤ h ≤ 17, -21 ≤ k ≤ 21, -37 ≤ l ≤ 35
Reflections collected	55240
Independent reflections	7296 [R _{int} = 0.0519, R _{sigma} = 0.0294]
Data/restraints/parameters	7296/0/410
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.086
Final R indexes [I ≥ 2σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.0431, wR ₂ = 0.1169
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.0480, wR ₂ = 0.1203
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	0.47/-0.43

Figure S8. The crystal structure of Me₄N[(1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C₃H₆-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1',2'-C₂B₉H₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)].CH₂Cl₂ (ORTEP view, 30% probability level).

Figure S9. The crystal packing in the structure of $\text{Me}_4\text{N}[(1-(4\text{-Ph-Triazolyl})\text{-C}_3\text{H}_6\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(1',2'\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3}'\text{-Co(III)}]\cdot\text{CH}_2\text{Cl}_2$ showing columns of the cobalt bis(dicarbollide) ions separated by layers of triazine rings. (ORTEP view, 40% probability level).

Crystal data and structure refinement for anionic $\text{Me}_4\text{N}[(1\text{-NH}_2\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(1',2'\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3}'\text{-Co(III)}]$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N4}$) and protonated form $\text{Me}_4\text{N}[(1\text{-NH}_2\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(1',2'\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3}'\text{-Co(III)}]\cdot\text{HCl}\cdot 1/2\text{MeOH}$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N4}\cdot\text{HCl}$)

A. Anionic $\text{Me}_4\text{N}[(1\text{-NH}_2\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(1',2'\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3}'\text{-Co(III)}]$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N4}$)

Experimental

This structure corresponds to anionic, unprotonated form isolated from experiment, when the reaction mixture was not acidified with diluted HCl and the product was isolated only using flash RP-chromatography and precipitated with Me_4NCl in water. Single crystals of $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{35}\text{B}_{18}\text{CoN}_2$ were grown from CH_2Cl_2 -Hexane. A suitable crystal was selected and measured on a XtaLAB Synergy, Dualflex, HyPix diffractometer, Rigaku. The crystal was kept at 100.00(10) K during data collection. Using Olex2 [1], the structure was solved with the SHELXT [2] structure solution program using Intrinsic Phasing and refined with the SHELXL [3] refinement package using Least Squares minimisation.

Crystal Data for $\text{C}_8\text{H}_{35}\text{B}_{18}\text{CoN}_2$ ($M=412.89$ g/mol): orthorhombic, space group $\text{Pna}2_1$ (no. 33), $a = 12.0186(7)$ Å, $b = 25.1173(15)$ Å, $c = 7.3524(4)$ Å, $V = 2219.5(2)$ Å³, $Z = 4$, $T = 100.00(10)$ K, $\mu(\text{Cu K}\alpha) = 5.990$ mm⁻¹, $D_{\text{calc}} = 1.236$ g/cm³, 13448 reflections measured ($7.038^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 156.248^\circ$), 4023 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0691$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.0402$) which were used in all calculations. The final R_1 was 0.0753 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and wR_2 was 0.2098 (all data).

Table S4. Crystal data and structure refinement for Me₄N[(1-NH₂-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀) (1',2'-C₂B₉H₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me₄N4).

Crystal data	
Identification code	CCDC 2359160
Empirical formula	C ₈ H ₃₅ B ₁₈ CoN ₂
Formula weight	412.89
Temperature/K	100.00(10)
Crystal system	orthorhombic
Space group	Pna2 ₁
a/Å	12.0186(7)
b/Å	25.1173(15)
c/Å	7.3524(4)
α/°	90
β/°	90
γ/°	90
Volume/Å ³	2219.5(2)
Z	4
ρ _{calc} /cm ³	1.236
μ/mm ⁻¹	5.990
F(000)	856.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.33 × 0.2 × 0.16
Data collection and refinement	
Radiation	Cu Kα (λ = 1.54184)
2θ range for data collection/°	7.038 to 156.248
Index ranges	-14 ≤ h ≤ 10, -30 ≤ k ≤ 31, -9 ≤ l ≤ 7
Reflections collected	13448
Independent reflections	4023 [R _{int} = 0.0691, R _{sigma} = 0.0402]
Data/restraints/parameters	4023/1/275
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.075
Final R indexes [I ≥ 2σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.0753, wR ₂ = 0.2005
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.0798, wR ₂ = 0.2098
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	1.00/-0.49
Flack parameter	0.081(9)

Figure S10. The crystal structure of the anionic form of $\text{Me}_4\text{N}[(1\text{-NH}_2\text{-}1,2\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(1',2'\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-}3,3'\text{-Co(III)}](\text{Me}_4\text{N}_4)$. (ORTEP view, 30% probability level).

Figure S11. The crystal packing in the structure of racemic crystal of $\text{Me}_4\text{N}[(1\text{-NH}_2\text{-}1,2\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(1',2'\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-}3,3'\text{-Co(III)}](\text{Me}_4\text{N}_4)$ showing presence of two pairs of enantiomers. (ORTEP view, 40% probability level).

B. Protonated form $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][(1\text{-NH}_2\text{-}1,2\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(1',2'\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-}3,3'\text{-Co(III)}]\cdot\text{HCl}$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N}_4\cdot\text{HCl}$)

Experimental

This structure corresponds to protonated form isolated from experiment, when the reaction mixture was acidified with diluted HCl (3M) and the product was isolated by extraction into Et_2O followed with flash RP-chromatography and precipitation with Me_4NCl in 3M HCl in 50% aqueous MeOH. Single crystals corresponding to composition $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{40}\text{B}_{18}\text{ClCoN}_2\text{O}$ were grown from CH_2Cl_2 -Hexane. A suitable crystal was selected and measured on a XtaLAB Synergy, Dualflex, HyPix diffractometer, Rigaku. The crystal was kept at 100.00(10) K during data collection. Using Olex2 [1], the structure was solved with the

SHELXT [2] structure solution program using Intrinsic Phasing and refined with the SHELXL [3] refinement package using Least Squares minimisation.

Crystal Data for $C_9H_{40}B_{18}ClCoN_2O$ ($M=481.39$ g/mol): triclinic, space group P-1 (no. 2), $a = 7.18070(10)$ Å, $b = 12.3450(2)$ Å, $c = 14.7955(2)$ Å, $\alpha = 102.8510(10)^\circ$, $\beta = 93.5410(10)^\circ$, $\gamma = 97.8660(10)^\circ$, $V = 1260.89(3)$ Å³, $Z = 2$, $T = 99.99(10)$ K, $\mu(\text{Cu K}\alpha) = 6.324$ mm⁻¹, $D_{\text{calc}} = 1.268$ g/cm³, 38805 reflections measured ($6.156^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 160.362^\circ$), 5309 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0552$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.0289$) which were used in all calculations. The final R_1 was 0.0489 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and wR_2 was 0.1420 (all data).

Table S5. Crystal data and structure refinement for $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][(\text{1-NH}_2\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10}) (\text{1',2'-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3'-Co(III)}]\cdot\text{HCl}$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N}4\cdot\text{HCl}$).

Crystal data	
Identification code	CCDC 2359155
Empirical formula	$C_9H_{40}B_{18}ClCoN_2O$
Formula weight	481.39
Temperature/K	99.99(10)
Crystal system	triclinic
Space group	P-1
$a/\text{Å}$	7.18070(10)
$b/\text{Å}$	12.3450(2)
$c/\text{Å}$	14.7955(2)
$\alpha/^\circ$	102.8510(10)
$\beta/^\circ$	93.5410(10)
$\gamma/^\circ$	97.8660(10)
Volume/Å ³	1260.89(3)
Z	2
$\rho_{\text{calc}}/\text{cm}^3$	1.268
μ/mm^{-1}	6.324
$F(000)$	500.0
Crystal size/mm ³	$0.26 \times 0.108 \times 0.083$
Data collection and refinement	
Radiation	Cu K α ($\lambda = 1.54184$)
2θ range for data collection/ $^\circ$	6.156 to 160.362
Index ranges	$-7 \leq h \leq 8, -15 \leq k \leq 15, -18 \leq l \leq 18$
Reflections collected	38805
Independent reflections	5309 [$R_{\text{int}} = 0.0552, R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.0289$]
Data/restraints/parameters	5309/6/409
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.092
Final R indexes [$I \geq 2\sigma(I)$]	$R_1 = 0.0489, wR_2 = 0.1389$
Final R indexes [all data]	$R_1 = 0.0529, wR_2 = 0.1420$
Largest diff. peak/hole / $e \text{ Å}^{-3}$	0.50/-0.59

Figure S12. The crystal structure of $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][(\text{1-NH}_2\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(\text{1',2'-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3'-Co(III)}].\text{HCl}$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N4}.$) HCl . The structure contains a disordered molecule of MeOH (ORTEP view, 30% probability level).

Major component of disorder

Minor component of disorder

Figure S13. The major (left) and minor (right) components of disorder in the structure of $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][(\text{1-NH}_2\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(\text{1',2'-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3'-Co(III)}].\text{HCl}$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N4}.$) HCl (ORTEP view, 30% probability level).

Figure S14. Crystal packing in the structure of $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][(\text{1-NH}_2\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(\text{1',2'-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3'-Co(III)}]\cdot\text{HCl}$ (Me_4N_4) $\cdot\text{HCl}$. The structure contains both enantiomers in the unit cell, and two disordered Me_4N^+ cations along with hydrochloride moieties participating on hydrogen bonding with neighboring NH_2 groups, and a disordered molecule of MeOH (ORTEP view, 40% probability level).

Crystal data and structure refinement for $\text{Me}_4\text{N}[(\text{1,1'-H}_2\text{N-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})_2\text{-3,3'-Co(III)}]$ (Me_4N_5)

Experimental

Single crystals corresponding to the formulation of $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{43}\text{B}_{18}\text{ClCoN}_{3.03}\text{O}$ were grown from CH_2Cl_2 -Hexane. A few drops of acetone were added to CH_2Cl_2 for dissolution. A suitable crystal was selected and measured on a XtaLAB Synergy, Dualflex, HyPix diffractometer, Rigaku. The crystal was kept at 100.00(10) K during data collection. Using Olex2 [1], the structure was solved with the SHELXT [2] structure solution program using Intrinsic Phasing and refined with the SHELXL [3] refinement package using Least Squares minimisation.

Crystal Data for $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{43}\text{B}_{18}\text{ClCoN}_{3.03}\text{O}$ ($M = 522.79$ g/mol): monoclinic, space group C2/c (no. 15), $a = 34.0535(11)$ Å, $b = 7.03111(18)$ Å, $c = 24.4552(9)$ Å, $\beta = 103.615(3)^\circ$, $V = 5690.9(3)$ Å³, $Z = 8$, $T = 100.00(10)$ K, $\mu(\text{Cu K}\alpha) = 5.656$ mm⁻¹, $D_{\text{calc}} = 1.220$ g/cm³, 74727 reflections measured ($5.34^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 156.434^\circ$), 5854 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.1277$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.0532$) which were used in all calculations. The final R_1 was 0.0614 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and wR_2 was 0.1578 (all data).

Table S6. Crystal data and structure refinement for Me₄N[(1,1'-H₂N-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₁)₂-3,3'-Co(III)]

Crystal data	
Identification code	CCDC 2359159
Empirical formula	C ₁₁ H ₄₃ B ₁₈ ClCoN _{3.02} O
Formula weight	522.79
Temperature/K	100.00(10)
Crystal system	monoclinic
Space group	C2/c
a/Å	34.0535(11)
b/Å	7.03111(18)
c/Å	24.4552(9)
α/°	90
β/°	103.615(3)
γ/°	90
Volume/Å ³	5690.9(3)
Z	8
ρ _{calc} /cm ³	1.220
μ/mm ⁻¹	5.656
F(000)	2177.0
Crystal size/mm ³	0.395 × 0.043 × 0.033

Data collection and refinement	
Radiation	Cu Kα (λ = 1.54184)
2θ range for data collection/°	5.34 to 156.434
Index ranges	-42 ≤ h ≤ 41, -8 ≤ k ≤ 8, -29 ≤ l ≤ 30
Reflections collected	74727
Independent reflections	5854 [R _{int} = 0.1277, R _{sigma} = 0.0532]
Data/restraints/parameters	5854/0/332
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.049
Final R indexes [I ≥ 2σ (I)]	R ₁ = 0.0614, wR ₂ = 0.1461
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.0831, wR ₂ = 0.1578
Largest diff. peak/hole / e Å ⁻³	0.60/-0.47

Figure S15. The crystal structure of the protonated form of $\text{Me}_4\text{N}[(1,1'\text{-NH}_2\text{-}1,2\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})_2\text{-}3,3'\text{-Co(III)}]\cdot\text{HCl}$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N5}$). HCl (ORTEP view, 30% probability level). The structure contains a hydrochloride moiety and a molecule of acetone used for dissolution.

Figure S16. The crystal packing in the structure of $\text{Me}_4\text{N}[(1,1'\text{-NH}_2\text{-}1,2\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})_2\text{-}3,3'\text{-Co(III)}]\cdot\text{HCl}$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N5}$). HCl , which contains 8 boron clusters along with charge compensating Me_4N^+ ions and acetone molecules. The racemic crystal contains both enantiomers in the unit cell. (ORTEP view, 40% probability level).

Crystal data and structure refinement for $\text{Me}_4\text{N}[(1\text{-Me}_3\text{Si-}1,2\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(1',2'\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-}3,3'\text{-Co(III)}]$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N6}$)

Experimental

Single crystals corresponding to the formulation of $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{42}\text{B}_{18}\text{CoNSi}$ were grown from CH_2Cl_2 -Hexane. A few drops of acetone were added to CH_2Cl_2 for dissolution. A suitable crystal was selected

and measured on a XtaLAB Synergy, Dualflex, HyPix diffractometer, Rigaku. The crystal was kept at 100.00(10) K during data collection. Using Olex2 [1], the structure was solved with the SHELXT [2] structure solution program using Intrinsic Phasing and refined with the SHELXL [3] refinement package using Least Squares minimisation.

Crystal Data for $C_{11}H_{42}B_{18}CoNSi$ ($M=470.05$ g/mol): orthorhombic, space group $Pca2_1$ (no. 29), $a = 31.698(4)$ Å, $b = 7.0938(7)$ Å, $c = 11.6377(13)$ Å, $V = 2616.9(5)$ Å³, $Z = 4$, $T = 99.99(11)$ K, $\mu(Cu K\alpha) = 5.550$ mm⁻¹, $D_{calc} = 1.193$ g/cm³, 25530 reflections measured ($9.428^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 155.954^\circ$), 5037 unique ($R_{int} = 0.1385$, $R_{sigma} = 0.1059$) which were used in all calculations. The final R_1 was 0.0647 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and wR_2 was 0.1723 (all data).

Table S7. Crystal data and structure refinement for $Me_4N[(1-Me_3Si-1,2-C_2B_9H_{10})(1',2'-C_2B_9H_{11})-3,3'-Co(III)]$

Crystal data	
Identification code	CCDC 2375075
Empirical formula	$C_{11}H_{42}B_{18}CoNSi$
Formula weight	470.05
Temperature/K	99.99(11)
Crystal system	orthorhombic
Space group	$Pca2_1$
$a/\text{Å}$	31.698(4)
$b/\text{Å}$	7.0938(7)
$c/\text{Å}$	11.6377(13)
$\alpha/^\circ$	90
$\beta/^\circ$	90
$\gamma/^\circ$	90
Volume/Å ³	2616.9(5)
Z	4
ρ_{calc}/cm^3	1.193
μ/mm^{-1}	5.550
F(000)	984.0
Crystal size/mm ³	$0.06 \times 0.041 \times 0.028$
Data collection and refinement	
Radiation	Cu $K\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.54184$)
2θ range for data collection/ $^\circ$	9.428 to 155.954
Index ranges	$-40 \leq h \leq 39$, $-8 \leq k \leq 8$, $-14 \leq l \leq 14$
Reflections collected	25530
Independent reflections	5037 [$R_{int} = 0.1385$, $R_{sigma} = 0.1059$]
Data/restraints/parameters	5037/1/297
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.046
Final R indexes [$I \geq 2\sigma(I)$]	$R_1 = 0.0647$, $wR_2 = 0.1410$
Final R indexes [all data]	$R_1 = 0.1056$, $wR_2 = 0.1723$
Largest diff. peak/hole / $e \text{ Å}^{-3}$	0.36/-0.70
Flack parameter	0.353(11)

Figure S17. The crystal structure of the $\text{Me}_4\text{N}[(1\text{-Me}_3\text{Si-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(1',2'\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3}'\text{-Co(III)}]$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N6}$) (ORTEP view, 30% probability level).

Figure S18. The crystal packing in the structure of $\text{Me}_4\text{N}[(1\text{-Me}_3\text{Si-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(1',2'\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3}'\text{-Co(III)}]$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N6}$). The racemic crystal contains both enantiomers in the unit cell. (ORTEP view, 40% probability level).

Crystal data and structure refinement for $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][(1\text{-H}_2\text{N-CH}_2\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})\text{-2-3,3}'\text{-Co(III)}]\cdot 2\text{HCl}$ (VIII)

This unpublished structure is given here for comparison. It demonstrates the uniform type of protonation over the series of C-substituted amino derivatives of the cobalt bis(dicarbollide) ion that proceed via the formation of hydrochlorides; $\text{-NH}_2\cdot n\text{HCl}$. This is dissimilar to B-substituted compounds containing NH_3^+ groups.⁷

Experimental

The compound was prepared according to a previously published procedure.⁸ The structure corresponds to the protonated form isolated from the experiment, when the reaction mixture was acidified with

diluted HCl (3M) and the product was isolated by extraction into Et₂O followed with chromatography. Single crystals corresponding to composition C₆H₃₀B₁₈CoN₂·C₄H₁₂N·2(Cl)·2(H₂O) were grown from CH₂Cl₂ (with addition of MeOH) -Hexane. For details on data collection and refinement see the general Experimental part above.

Table S8. Crystal data and structure refinement for **VIII**

Crystal data	
Identification code	CCDC 2374900
Chemical formula	C ₆ H ₃₀ B ₁₈ CoN ₂ ·C ₄ H ₁₂ N·2(Cl)·2(H ₂ O)
<i>M_r</i>	564.91
Crystal system, space group	Monoclinic, <i>P</i> 2 ₁ / <i>n</i>
Temperature (K)	150
<i>a</i> , <i>b</i> , <i>c</i> (Å)	7.4177(2), 14.4885(6), 27.846(1)
β (°)	91.368(1)
<i>V</i> (Å ³)	2991.79(18)
<i>Z</i>	4
Radiation type	MoKα
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.77
Crystal size (mm)	0.24 × 0.13 × 0.09
Data collection	
Diffractometer	Bruker D8 - Venture
Absorption correction	Multi-scan SADABS2016/2 - Bruker AXS area detector scaling and absorption correction Reference: Krause, L., Herbst-Irmer, R., Sheldrick G.M. & Stalke D., J. Appl. Cryst. 48 (2015) 3-10.
<i>T_{min}</i> , <i>T_{max}</i>	0.684, 0.746
No. of measured, independent and observed [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)] reflections	69938, 6881, 5401
<i>R_{int}</i>	0.093
(sin θ/λ) _{max} (Å ⁻¹)	0.650
Refinement	
<i>R</i> [<i>F</i> ² > 2σ(<i>F</i> ²)], <i>wR</i> (<i>F</i> ²), <i>S</i>	0.042, 0.099, 1.04
No. of reflections	6881
No. of parameters	345
No. of restraints	492
H-atom treatment	H atoms treated by a mixture of independent and constrained refinement
Δρ _{max} , Δρ _{min} (e Å ⁻³)	0.85, -0.62

Computer programs: Bruker Instrument Service vV6.2.3, *APEX3* v2016.5-0 (Bruker AXS), *SAINT* V8.37A (Bruker AXS Inc., 2015), *XT*, VERSION 2014/5, *SHELXL2019/1* (Sheldrick, 2019), *PLATON* (Spek, 2009).

Table S9. Hydrogen-bond geometry (Å, °) for **VIII**

<i>D</i> —H··· <i>A</i>	<i>D</i> —H	H··· <i>A</i>	<i>D</i> ··· <i>A</i>	<i>D</i> —H··· <i>A</i>
O2—H2W···Cl2	0.99(1)	2.39(1)	3.273(2)	148(1)
O2—H2V···Cl1 ⁱ	0.75(3)	2.52(3)	3.227(2)	158(4)
O1—H3V···Cl1	0.82(4)	2.41(4)	3.197(2)	163(4)
O1—H3W···Cl2	0.81(4)	2.27(4)	3.070(2)	168(3)
N1—H1A···Cl2 ⁱⁱ	0.91	2.20	3.1129(19)	178
N1—H1B···Cl1 ⁱⁱⁱ	0.91	2.36	3.204(2)	154
N1—H1C···O1	0.91	1.93	2.732(3)	146
N2—H21···O2	0.91	1.87	2.754(3)	165
N2—H22···Cl2 ^{iv}	0.91	2.50	3.280(2)	144
N2—H23···Cl1	0.91	2.32	3.190(2)	160

Symmetry codes: (i) $x+1, y, z$; (ii) $x-1, y, z$; (iii) $-x+1/2, y+1/2, -z+3/2$; (iv) $-x+3/2, y-1/2, -z+3/2$.

Figure S19. The crystal structure of the protonated form of $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][(\text{1,1}'\text{-NH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})_2\text{-3,3}'\text{-Co(III)}]\cdot\text{HCl}$ (Me_4NVIII). $\cdot\text{HCl}$ (ORTEP view, 40% probability level). The structure contains a hydrochloride moiety and two water molecules.

Figure S20. The formation of hydrogen bonds between the amino groups and the hydrochloride moiety in the structure of Me₄N[(1-H₂N-CH₂-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)₂-3,3'-Co(III)].2HCl.2H₂O (ORTEP view, 50% probability level).

Figure S21. The crystal packing in the structure of Me₄N[(1-H₂N-CH₂-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₁)₂-3,3'-Co(III)].HCl. (ORTEP view, 40% probability level).

Crystal data and structure refinement for [Me₄N][(1-H₂N-C₂H₄-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1',2'-C₂B₉H₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)].HCl (Me₄NIII)

This unpublished structure is given here for comparison. It demonstrates the uniform type of protonation over the series of C-substituted amino derivatives of the cobalt bis(dicarbollide) ion that proceed *via* the formation of hydrochlorides -NH₂.HCl. This is dissimilar to B-substituted compounds containing NH₃⁺ groups.⁷

Experimental

The compound was prepared according to a previously published procedure.⁸ The structure corresponds to the protonated form isolated from the experiment, when the reaction mixture was acidified with diluted HCl (3M) and the product was isolated by extraction into Et₂O followed with with chromatography. Single crystals corresponding to composition C_{16.5}H₆₉B₃₆ClC₂N₃O_{0.5} were grown from CH₂Cl₂ (with the addition of MeOH) -Hexane. A suitable crystal was selected and measured on

a XtaLAB Synergy, Dualflex, HyPix diffractometer, Rigaku. The crystal was kept at 100.00(10) K during data collection. Using Olex2 [1], the structure was solved with the SHELXT [2] structure solution program using Intrinsic Phasing and refined with the SHELXL [3] refinement package using Least Squares minimisation.

Crystal Data for $C_{16.5}H_{69}B_{36}ClCo_2N_3O_{0.5}$ ($M=860.21$ g/mol): monoclinic, space group C2/c (no. 15), $a = 30.1120(3)$ Å, $b = 9.50090(10)$ Å, $c = 34.0551(4)$ Å, $\beta = 110.8860(10)^\circ$, $V = 9102.67(18)$ Å³, $Z = 8$, $T = 100.00(10)$ K, $\mu(\text{Cu K}\alpha) = 6.392$ mm⁻¹, $D_{\text{calc}} = 1.255$ g/cm³, 155400 reflections measured ($5.556^\circ \leq 2\theta \leq 133.184^\circ$), 8059 unique ($R_{\text{int}} = 0.0867$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.0259$) which were used in all calculations. The final R_1 was 0.0424 ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) and wR_2 was 0.1192 (all data).

Table S10. Crystal data and structure refinement for $\text{Me}_4\text{N}[(1\text{-H}_2\text{N-C}_2\text{H}_4\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(1',2'\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3'}\text{-Co(III)}]\cdot\text{HCl}$

Crystal data	
Identification code	CCDC 2359154
Empirical formula	$C_{16.5}H_{69}B_{36}ClCo_2N_3O_{0.5}$
Formula weight	860.21
Temperature/K	100.00(10)
Crystal system	monoclinic
Space group	C2/c
$a/\text{\AA}$	30.1120(3)
$b/\text{\AA}$	9.50090(10)
$c/\text{\AA}$	34.0551(4)
$\alpha/^\circ$	90
$\beta/^\circ$	110.8860(10)
$\gamma/^\circ$	90
Volume/Å ³	9102.67(18)
Z	8
$\rho_{\text{calc}}/\text{g/cm}^3$	1.255
μ/mm^{-1}	6.392
$F(000)$	3552.0
Crystal size/mm ³	$0.474 \times 0.051 \times 0.041$
Data collection and refinement	
Radiation	Cu K α ($\lambda = 1.54184$)
2θ range for data collection/ $^\circ$	5.556 to 133.184
Index ranges	$-35 \leq h \leq 35$, $-11 \leq k \leq 10$, $-40 \leq l \leq 40$
Reflections collected	155400
Independent reflections	8059 [$R_{\text{int}} = 0.0867$, $R_{\text{sigma}} = 0.0259$]
Data/restraints/parameters	8059/0/601
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.038
Final R indexes [$I \geq 2\sigma(I)$]	$R_1 = 0.0424$, $wR_2 = 0.1155$
Final R indexes [all data]	$R_1 = 0.0475$, $wR_2 = 0.1192$
Largest diff. peak/hole / $e \text{ \AA}^{-3}$	0.57/-0.50

Figure S22. The presence of hydrogen bonds between the amino groups and the chloride anion in the structure of $\text{Me}_4\text{N}[(1\text{-H}_2\text{N-C}_2\text{H}_4\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(1',2'\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3'}\text{-Co(III)}]\cdot\text{HCl}$ (ORTEP view, 30% probability level). Selected interatomic distances (\AA) and angles ($^\circ$): N1-C14A 1.490 (3), N1-C14B 1.484(3), C13A-C14A 1.522(3), C1-C2 1.608(3), C1A-C2A 1.633(3), C1B-C2B 1.647(3), Co(3)-C1 2.042(2), Co(3)-C1A 2.112(2), Co(3)-C2A 2.073(2), C1-B4 1.725(3), C1-B5 1.685(3), C1-B6 1.733(3), C1A-B5A 1.712(3), C1A-B6A 1.734(3), C2-B7 1.699(3), C2-B11 1.705(3), C2-B6 1.733(3), N1-C13A 1.44A 108.48(19), N1-C14A-C13A 108.48(19), N2-C13B-C14B 108.79(19), C1A-Co3-B8 135.02(9), C13A-C1A-C2A 118.54(18), C13A-C1A-B4A 125.14(18), C13A-C1A-B6A 111.40(12), C14A-C1A-C1A 115.11(19), C1A-B4A-B8A 106.74(18).

Figure S23. The crystal packing in the structure of $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][(1\text{-H}_2\text{N-C}_2\text{H}_4\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(1',2'\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3'}\text{-Co}]\cdot\text{HCl}$, each Cl^- participates on hydrogen bonding with $\text{C}_{\text{cage}}\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-NH}_2$ groups from four neighboring boron clusters. The racemic crystal contains both enantiomers in the unit cell. (ORTEP view, 40% probability level).

NMR Spectra

NMR Spectra of $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][(\text{1-N}_3\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(\text{1',2'-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3'-Co(III)}] (\text{Me}_4\text{N}2)$

Figure S24. $^{11}\text{B}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR Spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N}2$ in CD_3OD

Figure S25. ^{11}B NMR Spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N}2$ in CD_3OD

Figure S26. ^1H NMR Spectrum of Me_4N_2 in CD_3OD

Figure S27. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me_4N_2 in CD_3OD

Figure S28. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me_4N_2 in CD_3OD

NMR Spectra of [Me₄N][(1,1'-N₃-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)₂-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me₄N3)

Figure S29. ¹¹B{¹H} NMR Spectrum of Me₄N3 in CD₃OD

Figure S30. ¹¹B NMR Spectrum of Me₄N3 in CD₃OD

Figure S31. ¹H NMR Spectrum of Me₄N₃ in CD₃OD

Figure S32. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me_4N_3 in CD_3OD

Figure S33. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me_4N_3 in CD_3OD

NMR Spectra of [Me₄N][(1-H₂N-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1',2'-C₂B₉H₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me₄N4)

Figure S34. ¹¹B{¹H} NMR Spectrum of Me₄N4 in (CD₃)₂CO

Figure S35. ¹¹B NMR Spectrum of Me₄N4 in (CD₃)₂CO

Figure S36. ^1H NMR Spectrum of Me_4N_4 in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S37. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me_4N_4 in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S38. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR Spectrum of Me_4N_4 in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

NMR Spectra of [Me₄N][(1,1'-NH₂-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)₂-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me₄N5)

Figure S39. ¹¹B {¹H} NMR Spectrum of Me₄N5 in (CD₃)₂CO

Figure S40. ¹¹B NMR Spectrum of Me₄N5 in (CD₃)₂CO

Figure S41. ^1H NMR Spectrum of Me_4N_5 in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S42. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR Spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N5}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S43. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR Spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N5}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

NMR Spectra of [Me₄N][(1-Me₃Si-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1',2'-C₂B₉H₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me₄N6)

Figure S44. ¹¹B{¹H} NMR Spectrum of Me₄N6 in (CD₃)₂CO

Figure S45. ¹¹B NMR Spectrum of Me₄N6 in (CD₃)₂CO

Figure S46. ^1H NMR Spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N6}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S47. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR Spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N6}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S48. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR Spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N6}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S49. $^{29}\text{Si}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR Spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N6}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

NMR Spectra of [Me₄N][(1,1'-Me₃Si-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)₂-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me₄N7)

Figure S50. ¹¹B{¹H} NMR Spectrum of Me₄N7 in (CD₃)₂CO

Figure S51. ¹¹B NMR Spectrum of Me₄N7 in (CD₃)₂CO

Figure S52. ^1H NMR Spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N}7$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S53. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR Spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N7}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S54. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR Spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N7}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S55. $^{29}\text{Si}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR Spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N7}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

NMR Spectra of [Me₄N][(1-N₃-C₂H₄-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1',2'-C₂B₉H₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me₄N8)

Figure S56. ¹¹B {¹H} NMR spectrum of Me₄N8 in (CD₃)₂CO

Figure S57. ¹¹B NMR spectrum of Me₄N8 in (CD₃)₂CO

Figure S58. ^1H NMR spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N8}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S59. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR Spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N8}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S60. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N8}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

NMR Spectra of $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][(\text{1-N}_3\text{-C}_3\text{H}_6\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(\text{1',2'-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3'}\text{-Co(III)}]$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N9}$)

Figure S61. ^{11}B $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N9}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S62. ^{11}B NMR spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N9}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S65. ^{13}C $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N9}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

NMR Spectra of $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][(\text{1,1}^{\prime}\text{-N}_3\text{-C}_2\text{H}_4\text{-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})_2\text{-3,3}^{\prime}\text{-Co(III)}]$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N10}$)

Figure S66. ^{11}B $\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N10}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S67. ^{11}B NMR spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N10}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S68. ^1H NMR spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N10}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S69. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR Spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N10}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S70. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N10}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

NMR Spectra of [Me₄N][(1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C₂H₄-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1',2'-C₂B₉H₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me₄N11)

Figure S71. ¹¹B{¹H} NMR spectrum of Me₄N11 in (CD₃)₂CO

Figure S72. ¹¹B NMR spectrum of Me₄N11 in (CD₃)₂CO

Figure S73. ^1H NMR spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N11}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S74. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR Spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N11}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S75. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of Me₄N11 in (CD₃)₂CO

NMR Spectra of [Me₄N][(1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C₃H₆-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1',2'-C₂B₉H₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)] (Me₄N12)

Figure S76. ¹¹B{¹H} NMR spectrum of Me₄N12 in (CD₃)₂CO

Figure S77. ¹¹B NMR spectrum of Me₄N12 in (CD₃)₂CO

Figure S78. ^1H NMR spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N12}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S79. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N12}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S80. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N12}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

NMR Spectra of $[\text{Me}_4\text{N}][(\text{1}-(\text{CO})\text{N}_3\text{-1,2-}\text{C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(\text{1',2'-}\text{C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3'-Co(III)}]$ ($\text{Me}_4\text{N13}$)

Figure S81. $^{11}\text{B}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N13}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S82. ^{11}B NMR spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N13}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S83. ^1H NMR Spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N13}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S84. $^1\text{H}\{^{11}\text{B}\}$ NMR Spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N13}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

Figure S85. $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectrum of $\text{Me}_4\text{N13}$ in $(\text{CD}_3)_2\text{CO}$

III. HR-MS SPECTRA

HRMS Spectrum of $[(1,2-C_2B_9H_{11})_2-3,3'-Co(III)]^-$ (1⁻)

Figure S86. HRMS spectrum of 1⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.

HRMS Spectrum of [(1-N₃-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1',2'-C₂B₉H₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)]⁻ (2⁻)

Figure S87. HRMS spectrum of 2⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.

HRMS Spectrum of $[(1,1'-N_3-1,2-C_2B_9H_{10})_2-3,3'-Co(III)]^-$ (**3**)

Figure S88. HRMS spectrum of **3**⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.

HRMS Spectrum of $[(1\text{-H}_2\text{N-1,2-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(1',2'\text{-C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})\text{-3,3'-Co(III)}]^-$ (4^-)

Figure S89. HRMS spectrum of 4^- with a calculated isotopic pattern.

HRMS Spectrum of $[(1,1'-\text{NH}_2-1,2-\text{C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})_2-3,3'-\text{Co(III)}]^-$ (**5**⁻)

Figure S90. HRMS spectrum of **5**⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.

HRMS Spectrum of [(1-Me₃Si-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1',2'-C₂B₉H₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)]⁻ (6⁻)

Figure S91. HRMS spectrum of 6⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.

HRMS Spectrum of [(1,1'-Me₃Si-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)₂-3,3'-Co(III)]⁻ (7)

Figure S92. HRMS spectrum of 7⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.

HRMS Spectrum of $[(1-N_3-C_2H_4-1,2-C_2B_9H_{10})(1',2'-C_2B_9H_{11})-3,3'-Co(III)]^-$ (**8**)

Figure S93. HRMS spectrum of **8**⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.

HRMS Spectrum of [(1-N₃-C₃H₆-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1',2'-C₂B₉H₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)]⁻ (9⁻)

Figure S94. HRMS spectrum of 9⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.

HRMS Spectrum of $[(1,1'-N_3-C_2H_4-1,2-C_2B_9H_{10})_2-3,3'-Co(III)]^-$ (10^-)

Figure S95. HRMS spectrum of 10^- with a calculated isotopic pattern.

HRMS Spectrum of [(1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C₂H₄-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1',2'-C₂B₉H₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)]⁻ (11⁻)

Figure S96. HRMS spectrum of 11⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.

HRMS Spectrum of [(1-(4-Ph-Triazolyl)-C₃H₆-1,2-C₂B₉H₁₀)(1',2'-C₂B₉H₁₁)-3,3'-Co(III)]⁻ (12⁻)

Figure S97. HRMS spectrum of 12⁻ with a calculated isotopic pattern.

HRMS Spectrum of $[(1-(\text{CO})\text{N}_3-1,2-\text{C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{10})(1',2'-\text{C}_2\text{B}_9\text{H}_{11})-3,3'-\text{Co}(\text{III})]^-$ (13^-)

Figure S98. HRMS spectrum of 13^- with a calculated isotopic pattern.

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